

Physico-Chemical Studies of metallic pollution in Jamshedpur River- Jharkhand, India

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Abstract :

Studies of heavy metals namely Iron, Chromium, Manganese, Cobalt, Nickel, Copper, Zinc, Cadmium and Lead as pollutants in river water. Waste water discharge samples of rivers around steel plant at Jamshedpur and Copper plant at Ghatshila were carried out from April, 2004 to October, 2006. Atomic Absorption spectrophotometric analysis of non-filterable residue of surface sediments for the heavy metals were made. The fractional analysis of the sediments for metals in four important phases, like the adsorbed and/or ion exchangeable, oxide coating, organic solids and crystalline phases was carried out. Total metal's concentration was also determined. The sum of the concentrations of metals in adsorbed, oxide coating and inorganic solid phases is available to biota. The crystalline phase is not available to biota. The results have been discussed and the concentration of metal available to biota have been estimated.

Keywords : Metal transport phases, surface sediments, pollutants, biota, Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) and self purification.

1. Introduction :

The chemical composition of the surface sediments and its variation at different sites in river receiving the treated and untreated waste water from domestic

and industrial sources have a profound impact on the water quality of the river basin. Water chemistry only assesses the effluent impact at the time of sampling while the surface sediments geo-chemistry gives a cumulative assessment of pollution. Surface Sediments analysis has been used to trace pollutant inputs and to anticipate the affects of these pollutants on water quality.

In this work, the surface sediments from different sites on the rivers Subarnarekha and Kharkai around Steel City of Jamshedpur and Industrial establishment of Hindustan Copper Corporation Limited at Moubhandar. Ghatshila were analysed for their multi element composition with a view to establish the relationship between the pollution of the rivers and the discharge of domestic and industrial waste waters.

2. Experimental - Sampling Sites :

i) Subarnarekha River -

- Site III A - Waste water discharge from Copper plant at Ghatshila.
- Site III B - River water sample at Ghatshila.
- Site II A - Discharge sample near Baridih.
- Site II B - River water sample near Baridih.

ii) Kharkai River (Near Adityapur) -

- Site I A - Discharge Sample.
- Site I B - River water sample.

A) Partitioning of Waste Water Discharge Sample :

The sample was transferred into two 1L measuring flasks separately and then filtered through Whatman filter paper (No. - 42) separately. Filtrate in all the cases was rejected. The residues in the above two cases were collected separately and treated as follows.

Residue - I :

The residue obtained after filtration of the waste water discharge sample along with the filter paper was treated with 20 ml Aqua regia and heated for 0.5 hour over water bath. It was then filtered through Whatman filter paper (No. - 42) and the volume was made upto 500ML with distilled water in a volumetric flask. The metals determined in this filtrate were the total metal concentration in the sample.

Residue - II :

The residue obtained after filtration of 1L of waste water discharge sample along with the filter paper was leached with 50 ml 0.5N $MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ solution for 7 hr. stirring from time to time and it was then filtered through Whatman filter paper (No. - 42). The filtrate was then made up to 500ml with distilled water in a volumetric flask for the determination of adsorbed and / or ion exchangeable heavy metals (Eisenreich - 1980). The residue left over on the filter paper along with the filter paper itself was then leached with 0.4N sodium pyrophosphate solution for 10 hours stirring from time to time and then filtered. The filtrate was then made up to 500ml and heavy metals associated with organic solid were estimated from this filtrate. The residue along with the filter paper is treated with 50ml 0.3 N HCl solution and heated at $90^{\circ}C$ for 0.5 hr. and then filtered. The filtrate was then made up to 500ml. Heavy metals in oxide coating were determined in the filtrate. The residue left on the filter paper along with the filter paper was then treated with 20ml Aqua regia and heated over water bath for 0.5 hr. It was then filtered and the volume of the filtrate made upto 250ml. The metal determined in this last filtrate was designated metal in crystalline state.

B) Partitioning of River Water Sample :

Similar procedure was followed for the determination of total concentration heavy metals and concentration of heavy metals in different phases.

The samples obtained as above were analysed for estimation of heavy metals such as Fe, Mn, Cr, Ni, Co, Cu, Zn, Cd and Pb by Atomic Absorption spectrophotometer.

3. Results and Discussions :

Chemical Parameters for the Samples from Six Sites are given in the tables :

Site - IIIA → Moubhandar, Ghatshila River → Subarnarekha
 Month → November Year → 2004
 Sample → Discharge pH → 2.26

	Fe	Cr	Mn	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Cd	Pb
Total metal concentration (in mg/L)	71.00	0.077	0.14	0.068	2.18	-	0.31	-	0.053
Concentration of metal available to biota (in mg/L)	28.1295	0.069	0.105	0.0575	1.167	-	0.253	-	0.0525
Percentage of metal available to biota.	36.62%	89.60%	75.00%	84.56%	53.53%	-	81.6%	-	99.06%

Site - IIIB → Moubhandar, Ghatshila River → Subarnarekha
 Month → November Year → 2004
 Sample → Discharge pH → 6.22

	Fe	Cr	Mn	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Cd	Pb
Total metal concentration (in mg/L)	10.905	-	0.135	0.19	0.32	0.257	0.467	-	0.055
Concentration of metal available to biota (in mg/L)	4.11	-	0.116	0.160	0.31	0.207	0.417	-	0.038
Percentage of metal available to biota.	37.69%	-	84.06%	84.21%	97.00%	80.54%	89.3%	-	69.10%

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Site - IIA → Bardiha Housing Colony River → Subarnarekha
 Month → May Year → 2005
 Sample → Discharge pH → 7.76

	Fe	Cr	Mn	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Cd	Pb
Total metal concentration (in mg/L)	71.825	0.605	0.329	0.021	0.0614	0.0565	0.824	-	-
Concentration of metal available to biota (in mg/L)	9.82	0.258	0.298	0.0195	0.0535	0.045	0.766	-	-
Percentage of metal available to biota.	55.10%	42.64%	90.60%	92.86%	87.13%	79.65%	92.96%	-	-

Site - IIB → IIB River → Subarnarekha
 Month → May Year → 2005
 Sample → River Water pH → 7.96

	Fe	Cr	Mn	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Cd	Pb
Total metal concentration (in mg/L)	12.935	0.060	0.231	-	0.070	0.022	0.29	-	-
Concentration of metal available to biota (in mg/L)	4.539	-	0.2135	-	0.0645	0.019	0.262	-	-
Percentage of metal available to biota.	35.1%	-	92.42%	-	92.14%	86.36%	90.34%	-	-

Site - IA → IA River → Kharkai
 Month → June Year → 2006
 Sample → Discharge pH → 8.32

	Fe	Cr	Mn	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Cd	Pb
Total metal concentration (in mg/L)	2.62	-	0.164	0.238	0.056	0.086	0.24	-	-
Concentration of metal available to biota (in mg/L)	1.2305	-	0.149	0.226	0.0385	0.07	0.206	-	-
Percentage of metal available to biota.	47.00%	-	90.85%	94.96%	68.75%	81.40%	85.83%	-	-

Site → IB

River → Kharkai

Month → June

Year → 2006

Sample → River Water

pH → 8.44

	Fe	Cr	Mn	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	Cd	Pb
Total metal concentration (in mg/L)	1.862	-	0.126	0.045	0.145	0.045	0.154	-	0.031
Concentration of metal available to biota (in mg/L)	0.6985	-	0.099	0.0425	0.073	0.0315	0.1155	-	0.030
Percentage of metal available to biota.	37.51%	-	78.60%	94.44%	50.34%	70.00%	75.00%	-	96.77%

Among the heavy metals, iron occurs in much higher concentration. Site - IIB (Subarnarekha river water at Baridih site) and site - IIIB (Subarnarekha river water at Moubhandar, Ghatshila) have higher values of total iron. Site - IB (Kharkai river water near Adityapur) has relatively lower value of total iron content. Sites - IB and IIB are near the waste water discharge from the industrial establishments in Jamshedpur, the Steel City. Site - IIIB is about 1Km downstream from the waste water discharge from Ghatshila copper plant. Sites - IIB and IIIB samples have high iron content.

Reddish brown suspensions were usually found at Sites - IIB and IIIB which might be due to the formation of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$, formed by the acidic waste water mixing the natural river water having bicarbonate alkalinity. The dissolved or ferrous iron can also be oxidized into insoluble ferric compounds (mostly ferric oxide) as the effluents are oxygenated and neutralized by river water. This type of condition was also found by Brush, Kalinowski and Miller (reference no. 11) in their work. In this work, the total iron content as determined by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer in river water samples varies from 1.862 mg/L to 12.935 mg/L and in discharge samples, varies from 2.62 mg/L to 71 mg/L. According to environmental pollution norms the general standard of iron concentration for discharge as environmental pollutant is 3 mg/L. According to WHO standard permissive value of Fe for drinking water is 0.3 ppm and 1 ppm is excessive.

Total chromium metal content as determined by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer was in the range from 0.077 mg/L to 0.605 mg/L in the discharge sample. In the river water sample chromium was found at Baridih site only and the concentration was 0.060 mg/L in the crystalline state. Chromium (VI) is the most toxic one. Waste water from different industries involving steel manufacture, chrome plating etc., is rich in Chromium content. Chromium enters into the water bodies in the form of chromate from cooling towers. CrO_4^{2-} solution is used in passivating the steel surface through the formation of a protective coating. The stable oxidation states of chromium are +3 and +6. Cr (III) can exist as $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_2^+$, $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_2^-$, $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$, $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_4^-$ depending on the pH. In aquatic environment, MnO_2 present in the sediment can oxidise Cr (III) to Cr (VI). Normal level of Cr (IV) in drinking water is 3 to 40ppb. The normal permissible limit being 50ppb.

Total manganese content in the river water samples as determined by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer were in the range from 0.126 mg/L to 0.231 mg/L. In the waste water discharge samples, total manganese content varies from 0.14 mg/L to 0.329 mg/L. Manganese frequently encounters in iron bearing water, although it is present usually to a much lesser extent than iron. According to WHO standard permissive value of Mn for drinking water is 0.1 ppm and 0.5 ppm is excessive.

Total cobalt (Co) concentration in river water samples varies from 0.045 mg/L to 0.19 mg/L with sites IB and IIIB as determined by Atomic Absorption

Spectrophotometer. Site IIIB has higher total cobalt content. At site IIB (Subarnarekha river water, Baridih Site), the cobalt concentration was almost Nil. In discharge samples total Cobalt ion concentration varies from 0.021 to 0.238 mg/L.

The total nickel (Ni) content in river water samples as determined by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer was in the range from 0.070 mg/L to 0.32 mg/L. In the discharge samples Ni ion concentrations varies from 0.056 mg/L to 2.18 mg/L. The general standard of Ni for discharge as pollutant (inland surface water) is 3.0 mg/L.

In river water sample the total copper concentration as determined by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer varies from 0.022 mg/L to 0.257 mg/L. In the discharge sample, total copper concentration varies from 0.0565 mg/L to 0.086 mg/L. The values of Cu^{++} ions are due to suspended solids, (M.J. Stiff - reference no. 13). M.J. Stiff has shown that copper may be present in polluted surface fresh waters, both associated with suspended solid and in different soluble chemical states. An analytical scheme was devised by him to differentiate quantitatively these soluble forms of copper. Analytical results showed that much of copper present in the river waters is associated with suspended solid and that soluble copper consists almost entirely of complexed forms. Site IIIB has highest copper content. According to WHO standard permissible value of copper in drinking water is 1 mg/L and 1.5 mg/L is excessive.

Aquatic environments are very sensitive to the presence of many trace elements. It has been shown that the growth rate of algae is affected by the presence of free Cu^{++} concentrations as low as 10^{-10} to 10^{-12}M . The presence of copper in the samples is a definite indication of its effect on aquatic environment in these rivers. The site IIIB water samples have low pH value. This low pH value of the site IIIB water sample is an indication to the absence of control on the treatment of waste water in the industrial establishment. Therefore urgent attention of the authorities is required for the treatment of the waste water.

The discharge of the metal ions like Cu^{++} at this pH (2.26) at site IIIA must have affected the aquatic environment of Subarnarekha to a very large extent rendering the water even unfit for agricultural purposes.

Total zinc concentration as determined by AAS varies from 0.24 mg/L to 0.824 mg/L in the discharge sample and in river water sample varies from 0.154 mg/L to 0.467mg/L. According to WHO standard permissive value for drinking water is 5 ppm and 15 ppm is excessive. Hence the values of zinc concentration in river water samples lie below the permissive value for this purpose, but the effect of the concentration of zinc to fishes and algae growth should be evaded. Zinc is very toxic to fish. According to Schott (reference no. 12), owing to an increase in the free CO₂ concentration of water supply to fish tanks containing trout, sufficient zinc was dissolved from newly galvanised pipes to give a zinc concentration of 0.15 ppm, which proved fatal to the fishes. A number of cases of mortality among fishes caused by the presence of zinc in solution have also been found by him.

Both in water and in aquatic floating plants, the trace element decreases in the order of Fe, Mn, Zn, Cu....., but in submerged and free floating plants, the order is Mn, Fe, Zn, Cu..... Free floating plants accumulate high trace elements, but after their short life cycle, the trace elements return to the water and also accumulate partially in bottom sediments, where they serve as source of secondary pollution of the reservoirs. The Mn and Cu uptake by aquatic plants play the main role in decreasing the pollution of water and sediments with these trace elements. Fe and Zn are removed both by their biogenic accumulation by the plants and by physio-chemical factor of Fe precipitation as Fe-hydroxide and Zn-Sorption on fine particles suspended in water (reference no. 4).

Lead metal concentration was determined by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer. Lead was found to be almost nil at sites IA, IIA and IIB but found at the sites IB, IIIA and IIIB. The total lead metal concentration in river water samples varies from 0.031 mg/L to 0.055 mg/L. Total lead content in the discharge sample of site IIIA was 0.053 mg/L.

In fresh water, PbCO₃ and Pb(CO₃)₂ - are the major species. Carbonates increase with increase in pH between "6 - 8"; at higher pH the hydroxy species dominate. Lead carbonates (and basic carbonates) are found in sediments in rivers and lakes. In the water bodies, the soluble Pb-compounds are gradually converted into insoluble PbS in part. Lead compounds are also sorbed by iron-manganese oxides.

Recommended minimum pH levels for aquatic life.

MINIMUM pH LEVELS

pH levels can fluctuate daily due to pollutants was waste water discharge the water. The degree of change depends on the Alkalinity of the water.

At an river pH of 8.3 carbonate levels are high enough for coral building. As CO_2 increases and pH decreases carbonate level will quickly drop below optimum levels.

4. Conclusion :

These data about the occurrence of Fe, Cr, Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn and Pb in the various available and unavailable metal phases would help in determining the effect of these metals on the crops and other biota. The higher concentration of the heavy metals in water also prevents the self purification of water and produces adverse effect on aquatic lives. During the evolution process, life did not meet these toxic elements and this is why it did not evolve any efficient mechanism to cope with these elements. Consequently, the tolerance limit given by the threshold value for a toxic element is generally very low and toxicity, i.e. deleterious effect, starts even for a minuscule concentration. However, it needs further study on the co-relation of the concentration of these metals in the various phases and their toxicological and other effects.

Heavy metals have been proved to be toxic to both human and environment health owing to their toxicity and their possible bioaccumulation, these compounds should be subject to mandatory monitoring. Several suitable separation and detection methods are available for laboratories engaged daily in routine analysis of a large number of biological or environmental sample.

It may be concluded that a holistic approach is essential for the abatement of environmental pollution. So, it is very necessary to control and reduce this pollution

as much as possible so that all the living beings would become healthy in harmless environment by which or human society would be benefited much with their safe life and good health.

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